

Borate complexes in solution. Part-III. Mixed ligand complex formation of cobalt-, nickel- and zinc(II) with boric acid and some (N,N) bidentate ligands

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Equilibrium study on the mixed ligand complex formation of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} , hereafter $\text{M}(\text{II})$, with boric acid and some (N,N) bidentate ligands, viz. 2,2'-bipyridine 1,10-phenanthroline and ethylenediamine provides evidence of formation of binary $\text{M}(\text{N,N})^{2+}$, $\text{M}(\text{H}_2\text{BO}_4)^-$ and ternary mononuclear $\text{M}(\text{N,N})(\text{H}_2\text{BO}_4)^-$ and binuclear $\text{M}_2(\text{N,N})_2(\text{BO}_4)^-$ complexes in solution. Formation constants of the complexes at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ have been determined in aqueous solution at a fixed ionic strength, $I = 0.1 \text{ M}$ (NaNO_3) and correlated with electronic structure, stereochemistry of metal ions and metal-ligand π -bonding. Complex formation equilibria have been elucidated with the aid of specification curves.

Enhancement of acidity of boric acid due to formation of chelated structure around the tetravalent electron deficient boron(III) is well known^{1,2}. Transition metal complexes having two coordinated H_2O molecules, or two OH groups or one H_2O molecule and one OH group in *cis*-positions are structurally similar to 1,2-*cis*-diols with regard to formation of chelate structures with boron(III) and consequent enhancement of acidity of otherwise weak boric acid. Equilibrium studies on the complex formation of H_3BO_3 with some *cis*-diaqua- Co^{III} complexes³ and with Cu^{II} ion in presence of some typical (N,N) bidentate ligands⁴ indicated the formation of mononuclear and binuclear mixed ligand borate complexes in solution. The present paper describes the results of an equilibrium study on the complex formation of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} , hereafter $\text{M}(\text{II})$, with H_3BO_3 in the presence of some such typical (N,N) bidentate ligands, viz. 2,2'-bipyridine (bipy), 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) and ethylenediamine (en), hereafter L, by potentiometric method in aqueous solution at a fixed ionic strength, $I = 0.1 \text{ M}$ (NaNO_3) at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Results and Discussion

Boric acid (H_3BO_3) in dilute aqueous solution titrates as a weak monobasic Lewis acid⁵, accepting OH^- , according to equilibrium (1),

Complex formation equilibria of the $\text{M}(\text{II})$ ions with H_3BO_3 - LH_2^{2+} mixtures (L = bipy, phen and en) occur at pH values much lower than the buffer regions corresponding to the hydrolytic equilibria of the $\text{M}(\text{aq})^{2+}$ ions, so the hydroxo complexes, $\text{M}(\text{OH})^+$ and $\text{M}(\text{OH})_2$ etc. are not involved in the formation of $\text{M}(\text{II})$ -L-borate complexes. Speciation cur-

ves (Fig. 1) of the 1 : 1 : 1 and 2 : 2 : 1 $\text{M}(\text{II}) : \text{LH}_2^{2+} : \text{H}_3\text{BO}_3$ systems (L = bipy and phen) show that predominant metal containing species at the start of com-

Fig. 1. Species distribution curves for the Co^{II} -bipy- H_3BO_3 system; (a) $\text{Co}^{\text{II}} : \text{bipy} : \text{H}_3\text{BO}_3 = 1 : 1 : 1$, (b) $\text{Co}^{\text{II}} : \text{bipy} : \text{H}_3\text{BO}_3 = 2 : 2 : 1$: (1) H_3BO_3 , (2) bipyH_2^{2+} , (3) bipyH^+ , (4) $\text{Co}(\text{bipy})^{2+}$, (5) $\text{Co}(\text{bipy})(\text{H}_2\text{BO}_4)^-$, (6) $\text{Co}_2(\text{bipy})_2(\text{BO}_4)^-$, $F_M = \text{Co}^{2+}$.

plex formation (pH 2-3) are the 1 : 1 binary $\text{M}(\text{L})^{2+}$ complexes, which are formed according to the equilibrium (2),

With rise of pH (>3) the 1 : 1 : 1 mixtures consumes 3 moles of base per mole of $M(L)^{2+}$, whereas, the 2 : 2 : 1 mixtures consume 2.5 moles of base per mole of $M(L)^{2+}$. These indicate the formation of mononuclear 1 : 1 : 1 and binuclear 2 : 2 : 1 mixed ligand borate complexes, $M(L)(H_2BO_4)^-$ and $M_2(L)_2(BO_4)^-$ according to equilibria (3) and (4), respectively,

With the 2 : 2 : 1 $Zn^{II} : LH_2^{2+} : H_3BO_3$ system, however, an additional equilibrium (5) is also indicated, possibly because of relatively lower formation constants of the binary $Zn(L)^{2+}$ complexes,

The $M(II) : enH_2^{2+} : H_3BO_3$ systems are different from the corresponding systems with $L = bipy$ and $phen$. The speciation curves (Fig. 2) indicate that the initial step in both 1 : 1 : 1 and 2 : 2 : 1 $M(II) : enH_2^{2+} : H_3BO_3$ mixtures, with $M = Co, Ni$ and Zn , is the formation of binary $M(H_2BO_4)^-$ complexes according to equilibrium (6),

With rise of pH, the mononuclear and binuclear mixed ligand borate complexes are formed according to equilibria (7) and (8), respectively,

The $\log K^M [M(L)(H_2BO_4)]$ and $\log K^M [M_2(L)_2(BO_4)]$ values (Table 1) are found to be in the Irving-Williams order⁶ : $Co^{II} < Ni^{II} < Cu^{II} > Zn^{II}$ as expected. Stability for mixed ligand borate complexes of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} fall in the ligand (L) order : $phen > bipy > en$ and that of Zn^{II} in the order : $en > phen > bipy$. Stability of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} mixed ligand borate complexes with $L = bipy$ and $phen$ arises from $M(d\pi) \rightarrow L(\pi)$ bonding with the aromatic π -system of $phen$ and $bipy$, whereas such effect is absent in Zn^{II} complexes. Relatively higher stability of $Zn(en)(H_2BO_4)^-$ and $Zn_2(en)_2(BO_4)^-$ complexes may be due to greater conformational flexibility provided by en for tetrahedral coordination of ligands around Zn^{II} .

Table 1. Formation constants* of mixed ligand $M(II)$ -L-borate complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} with $L = bipy, phen$ and en in aqueous solution.

$I = 0.1 M (NaNO_3), temp. = 25^\circ$

(i) Portion-ligand constants :

	borate	bipy	phen	en
pK_2^H	—	1.32	1.90	7.10
pK_1^H	9.00	4.23	4.96	9.89

(ii) 1 : 1 $M(II)$ -ligand binary constants ($\log K_{M(L)}^M$) :

M	borate	bipy	phen	en
Co	1.56	6.06	7.83	5.62
Ni	2.17	7.13	8.64	6.96
Cu^4	3.55	7.80	9.14	10.44
Zn	1.34	5.15	6.22	5.61

(iii) 1 : 1 : 1 $M(II)$ -L-borate ternary constants ($\log K^M [M(L)(H_2BO_4)]$) :

M	borate	bipy	phen	en
Co	—	8.78	10.12	8.47
Ni	—	9.95	11.38	10.09
Cu	—	10.97	11.60	12.10
Zn	—	8.26	8.45	8.52

(iv) 2 : 2 : 1 $M(II)$ -L-borate ternary constants ($\log K^M [M_2(L)_2(BO_4)]$) :

M	borate	bipy	phen	en
Co	—	16.27	17.06	15.68
Ni	—	17.03	17.96	17.02
Cu	—	18.25	18.57	21.20
Zn	—	13.73	14.76	15.39

*Limits of error in the constants : $\pm(0.02 \sim 0.05)$ in log scale; stability constants of Cu^{II} complexes are included from Ref. 4 for comparison.

Fig. 2. Species distribution curves for the Ni^{II} -en- H_3BO_3 system; (a) $Ni^{II} : en : H_3BO_3 = 1 : 1 : 1$, (b) $Ni^{II} : en : H_3BO_3 = 2 : 2 : 1$; (1) H_3BO_3 , (2) enH_2^{2+} , (3) enH^+ , (4) $Ni(H_2BO_4)^-$, (5) $Ni(en)(H_2BO_4)^-$, (6) $Ni_2(en)_2(BO_4)^-$; $F_M = Ni^{2+}$.

Experimental

Boric acid, 2,2'-bipyridine, 1,10-phenanthroline, sodium nitrate and nitric acid were of A.R. grade. Ethylenediamine (A.R.) was purified by distillation and converted into its dinitrate salt, $en.2HNO_3$, air-dried and analysed. Metal nitrate solutions were prepared by dissolving freshly precipitated metal hydroxides in standard HNO_3 and stand-

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ardised by combined acid-base, ion exchange and complexometric titrations⁷

The equilibrium study involved pH-metric titrations in aqueous medium of a series of solutions of equal volumes (25 ml) containing known amounts (0.001–0.01 M) of the ligands H₃BO₃ and/or LH₂²⁺ (L = bipy, phen and en) containing known amount (0.01 M) of free HNO₃ in the absence and in the presence of known amounts (0.001–0.002 M) of metal nitrates keeping M(II) : LH₂²⁺ : H₃BO₃ ratios 1 : 1 : 1 and 2 : 2 : 1. with carbonate free standard 0.1 M NaOH solution⁸, maintaining a fixed ionic strength, *I* = 0.1 M (NaNO₃), following the procedure described earlier⁴.

Ionic product of water at the experimental temperature and activity coefficient of H⁺ ion at the experimental ionic strength were obtained from literature^{9,10}. Analytical concentrations of H⁺ ion corresponding to the pH-meter readings were obtained by the usual procedure¹¹. Formation constants (Table 1) were calculated with the aid of SCOGS computer programme¹², run on a IBM 300GL personal computer. The constants were refined over several cycles of operation and the values corresponding to minimum standard deviations were accepted. The values for the M^{II}-L complexes were comparable to the literature values under identical/nearly identical conditions obtained by previous workers¹³. Complex formation equilibria were elucidated with the help of the speciation curves obtained as computer outputs.

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